

Field	Value to be filled (defaults added where applicable)	Options	Note
Title	Predictors available for spatial modelling for the optimization of marine spatial protection in the Baltic Sea. Protect Baltic project - Enabling comprehensive effective and efficient protection and restoration measures for a resilient Baltic Sea ecosystem		
Date	01.06.2025		
Abstract	<p>This data set spans multiple oceanographic, chemical, physical, and geomorphological layers. Bathymetric complexity was captured through broad- and fine-scale Bathymetric Position Indices, along with seafloor depth, slope, and ruggedness. Seafloor characteristics included sediment type* and wave exposure estimates. Water column properties were described using measurements of oxygen, salinity, temperature, pH, and nutrient concentrations (nitrate and phosphate) at both bottom and surface layers, each described by mean values and standard deviations. Stratification were characterized by Secchi depth, mixed layer depth, and sea ice concentration. Productivity was approximated by chlorophyll-a concentration. Surface and subsurface variability in wave conditions and satellite-derived sea surface temperature were also collected. Swedish sediment information published with permission from the Swedish Maritime Authority: Decision 23-06009 (12 Sep 2024).</p> <p>To prepare the layers, we applied a procedure designed to iteratively extrapolate missing values in a raster layer by applying a moving window mean filter. It first aligns the input raster to the target grid (Baltic Sea grid at 250 m resolution) using a specified projection method, then repeatedly fills in missing data based on the mean of neighboring cells within a circular window of user-defined size (2 in this case). This iterative process continues until either all missing values are filled or a predefined number of iterations is reached, with early termination if convergence occurs. This procedure ensures that extrapolation respects the spatial extent of the reference grid and provides progress updates during processing.</p> <p>* Swedish sediment information published with permission from the Swedish Maritime Authority: Decision 23-06009 (12 Sep 2024).</p>		
Simple			
Point of contact	HELCOM Secretariat		
Email	data@helcom.fi		
GEMET - INSPIRE themes, version 1.0	2, 10, 13, 28		
GEMET keywords	chemical oceanography, ocean current, oceanography, ocean temperature, physical oceanography		
Spatial representation type	Grid	Vector Grid Text, table	
Spatial resolution	250 m		
Metadata language	English		

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Topic category	Environment Oceans	Biota Boundaries Climatology, meteorology, atmosphere Economy Elevation Environment Geoscientific information Health Imagery base maps earth cover Intelligence military Inland waters Location Oceans Planning cadastre Society Structure Transportation	
Temporal extent begin date (start of data collection)		2010	
Temporal extent end date (end of data collection)		2023	
Used coordinate reference system	EPSG:3035		
Note:			
When published in MADS there are no restrictions for the data downloads/use			
All special features / exceptions in the file need to be explained in "Abstract" -section			
You can check examples from: HELCOM Metadata catalogue (not all of them are in exemplary condition :))			